

Evaluating k -mer Transformations for Cache Coherence and Uniformity

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k -mer indexes are essential tools for the comparative analysis of both assembled and unassembled datasets across various applications. While probabilistic indexes relying on dense encoding are known for their cost efficiency, exact k -mer indexes are crucial for users requiring precise results or access to specific matching k -mer sequences. The state of the art in sparse representation, capitalizing on the ability to "assemble" k -mers, is essentially static. In contrast, quotienting techniques that combine dense and sparse encoding offer a dynamic alternative and become increasingly memory-efficient as the size of the k -mer set expands. However, the non-uniform distribution of k -mer sequences, often resulting from biological phenomena, can negatively affect performance. To address this issue, k -mer transform aiming for a uniform distribution have been proposed. More recently, an orthogonal strategy optimizing the shared prefixes of successive k -mers has been introduced to reduce cache misses and enhance throughput. This study implements and evaluates k -mer transformations, assessing their impact on the uniformity of distribution and optimization of shared prefixes. Our analysis aims to identify the most effective transformations for specific use cases, thereby improving the efficiency and applicability of quotienting methods.

Availability and implementation:

We wrote our benchmark as an open-source C++ library under the AGPL3 license, available at <https://github.com/cagret/bijecthash>. It is designed as a user-friendly tool and comes with detailed instructions to add custom transform.

Introduction

The handling of massive data sets has become a crucial aspect of computational genomics. The surge in accessible sequence data from various sources has prompted advancements in genomics and adjacent disciplines, yet it has also introduced significant computational challenges in managing extensive sequencing studies. Notably, k -mer-based approaches have emerged as an efficient framework for sequence comparison. These methods offer a notable advantage in that they can process both assembled and unassembled sequences, efficiently filtering out sequencing errors based on k -mer abundance.

With recent progress in dedicated data structures, k -mers are now very efficiently indexed and applied to a wide range of bioinformatics tasks such as assembly(1), correction(2), quantification(3), and dataset comparison (4), especially in de novo or large-scale contexts where the alignment-free aspect allows methods to scale to large instances.

This work presents a study on optimizing such k -mer set representations. A first idea could be to represent the complete k -mer space in a dense way using a bijective function that maps k -mers to their integer representation. However, the vastness of k -mer space, which grows exponentially with the length of k , makes complete representation impractical for larger k values, even within a compressed scheme (5). For example, $k=20$ leads to $\approx 10^{12}$ k -mers, and $k=31$ leads to 10^{18} k -mers.

To avoid such exponential explosion when relying on dense encoding, a strategy employed by k -mer methods to achieve large scalability is to use surjective functions to map k -mers to integers within a limited range, often utilizing data structures such as Bloom filters (6, 7). This technique avoids the exponential memory requirements of exact dense encoding, representing the entirety of k -mer space with a constant memory footprint. Despite the advantages of fixed memory usage, this approach introduces two main issues: collisions, where distinct k -mers are mapped to the same integer, potentially leading to false positives, and the inability to revert to the original k -mer sequences, which can be crucial for certain applications.

To address these limitations, some works have explored how to optimize exact and sparse k -mer representations. Although direct k -mer encoding is highly memory-intensive, requiring $2k$ bits per k -mer for the naïve and broadly used encoding, methods such as Spectrum Preserving String Sets (8) have been developed to compactly represent sets of k -mers, thereby reducing the memory required for k -mer encoding. They exploit the fact that two successive k -mers overlapping by $k-1$ can be "assembled" into a sequence of only $k+1$ nucleotides. This concept extends to various forms of sequence representation(9). A main drawback of such k -mer representations is their static nature as they need to be constructed from a fixed set.

In order to allow dynamic insertions of k -mers in the set, another approach relies on quotienting strategies that leverage the fact that every prefix of length P will be present within the k -mer dataset, encoding only suffixes associated with each possible prefix of size P . This allows dynamic insertion as k -mers can be efficiently handled independently. This methodology serves as

a middle ground between dense and sparse encoding techniques, densely representing the 4^P P -sized prefixes while sparsely indexing their suffixes. The benefit of this method lies in the implicit encoding of the prefix at a fixed, yet exponentially increasing cost, with only the suffix being explicitly encoded and it provide the interesting property that larger set are more memory efficient by being able to encode more bits implicitly. A first idea to directly insert k -mers sequence as in *RedOak* (10). However, this approach is penalized by the fact that genomes are far from uniformly distributed sequences due to biological mechanisms such as repeats (11) or biased GC content (12, 13). This mechanically incurs a non-uniform k -mer distribution that indexes such tools with both empty bins and very large ones. An improvement is to rely on bijective transformations that render the distribution of k -mer images more uniform. Methods like the Counting Quotient Filter (14) relying on such approaches have reported nearly perfect distributions using revertible hash functions, such as the Thomas Wang functions.

Another point to take into account for such transform is the memory locality. When using nearly perfect uniform bijections like the Thomas Wang function, two successive k -mers extracted from a sequence to be indexed or queried will have very different images and will be located in distinct places in memory, generating cache misses and leading the processing to wait to access the corresponding data. Such cache misses are the actual bottleneck of many applications in bioinformatics that index large amounts of data. To limit this problem, it has been proposed to use in injective transform based on minimal rotations (Lyndon words) of k -mers in CBL (15). This transform optimizes the likelihood for consecutive overlapping k -mers to share a large suffix, thereby being located within the same substructure. Since most applications analyze all k -mers derived from longer sequences, querying consecutive k -mers reduces cache misses and overall improves throughput. Another approach is to use the concept of minimizers(16), to partition k -mers, using the fact that successive k -mers tend to share the same minimizer (17) to limit the number of cache misses (7, 18), but how to efficiently design a k -mer transform exploiting such properties is yet to be defined.

This raises an intriguing question about the extent to which these two objectives, cache coherence and satisfactory uniform binning, are mutually exclusive. Is it possible to achieve some cache coherence along with uniform binning? What solutions have been proposed in this regard, and how do they fare in balancing these two criteria? To address these queries, we have developed a benchmark to evaluate known k -mer transformations, providing a practical foundation for this line of investigation.

Methods

To assess the performance of different k -mer transformation methods, we developed a benchmark in C++ that takes a dataset in FASTA/FASTQ format and computes statistics on the produced image set for each desired transformation. The idea behind the benchmark design is to allow users to easily add their own transforms. The pipeline can be run with all available transforms or just with a subset to avoid cluttered plots or unnecessary resource usage. Following the same principle, several k -mer size and prefix size can be evaluated to provide precise analysis. To demonstrate its usage and to display some preliminary results we wrote a first set of transforms described in this section. To simplify complex transform evaluation, any available transform can be composed for evaluation.

A. Implementation details. The benchmark utilizes parallelization and various optimization techniques to efficiently process tasks. It follows producer-consumer pattern (file reading as k -mer producer, index writing as k -mer consumer) and the multiple reader-single writer pattern. Unlike traditional approaches that generally give higher priority to readers, a simple heuristic is implemented to adjust priority based on the queue sizes of readers and writers. When a new reader joins the queue, they wait if the writer's queue is longer. Readers proceed once their queue is shorter than the writers', and they can read after any currently writing writer finishes. Similarly, a writer waits if there are more waiting readers, and only one writer can write at a time, starting only after all readers have finished reading. For optimization, the benchmark employs a circular queue for storing k -mers, which is more memory-efficient than using a list or an array. It also rely on atomic operations to prevent race conditions when accessing the queue or the index. Techniques such as `yield()` and `sleep_for()` are used to prevent threads from consuming too many CPU resources while waiting.

B. Available Transforms.

B.1. Identity. As a baseline, we keep the original k -mer sequence. This transform is trivially bijective.

B.2. Inverse. The sequence in the reverse order. This transform is trivially bijective.

B.3. Canonical. The k -mer and its reverse complement are compared, and the one that is lexicographically minimal often dubbed canonical is returned. This transform is surjective since all noncanonical k -mers does not have a inverse and all canonical one does.

B.4. Cyclic. Cyclic is a simple rotation of the k -mer using an offset. This transform is bijective given the offset is known.

B.5. ZigZag. ZigZag is a nucleotide permutation transform that interleaves the k -mer prefix and suffix. The odd nucleotides of the transform are the nucleotides of the prefix, and the even nucleotides of the transform are the nucleotides of the suffix. This transform is bijective.

B.6. PermutationNuc. The PermutationNuc is a deterministic permutation of the nucleotides of the k -mer using a predefined seed. This transform is bijective given the seed is known.

B.7. PermutationBin. The PermutationBin first converts the k -mer into a binary representation, then applies a deterministic bit-by-bit permutation on this binary representation like PermutationNuc. This transform is bijective given the seed is known.

B.8. IntHash. We used Thomas Wang's invertible hash function based on xorshifts known for their cost efficiency, as used in minimap (19). This transform is bijective.

B.9. Gab. For completeness we also used the GAB revertible hash function used by HackGap (20) that aims specifically to have well distributed bins. This transform is bijective.

B.10. Lyndon. Lyndon is a transform based on Lyndon words, as inspired by CBL (15). The input k -mer rotations are computed, and the minimal one by lexicographic order is returned. This transform is injective and not bijective in practice, as the original k -mer start position has to be encoded to retrieve the original sequence. While it is possible to get a bijection by using the rank and unrank operations across Lyndon words, they are computationally expensive in practice, with complexities of $\mathcal{O}(n^2)$ and $\mathcal{O}(n^3)$, respectively (21). We chose not to implement them in this work.

B.11. Minimizers. The concept of a minimizer refers to the smallest m -mer within a k -mer, determined by a specific ordering, such as lexicographical order. Minimizers are often used to partition k -mers into substructures, benefiting from the fact that successive k -mers have a high probability of having the same minimizers (17). This transform compute the k -mer minimizer and arrange the sequence by placing the minimizer first, followed by the preceding and succeeding nucleotides, respectively. This way, we expect that successive k -mers will share a large prefix and be placed in the same bins. This transform is injective and not bijective as the minimizer position has to be encoded to retrieve the original sequence. It is yet unknown if a bijective transform putting minimizer in prefix is achievable in some conditions.

B.12. BWT. The Burrows-Wheeler Transform (BWT) is a highly effective transformation technique used in bioinformatics for optimizing sequence compression (22). Typically, BWT employs an end-of-sequence symbol, such as \$, essential for reversing the transform. To fit our benchmark behavior we used an alternative approach for maintaining a four-letter alphabet involves recording the symbol's position within the sequence. As mentioned earlier, this requires additional information, leading to an injective non-bijective function.

C. Evaluation Metrics. To evaluate the performance of the different k -mer transformations, we consider several metrics that capture various aspects of their behavior and effectiveness.

C.1. Uniformity. One of the key objectives of k -mer transformations is to achieve a uniform distribution of the transformed k -mers across the available bins. A uniform distribution ensures that the k -mers are evenly spread out optimizing storage efficiency.

C.2. Locality. Another important aspect of k -mer transformations is their ability to preserve locality, meaning that k -mers that are close to each other in the original sequence should remain close after the transformation. Locality is crucial for reducing cache misses and improving the performance of downstream applications that process k -mers sequentially. To quantify locality, we measure the average longest common prefix (LCP) between consecutive k -mers in the transformed space. A larger LCP indicates better locality preservation.

C.3. Reversibility. The ability to revert the transformed k -mers back to their original form is a desirable property for certain applications. Bijective transformations allow for perfect reversibility, while injective transformations require additional information to be stored for reversal. We classify each transformation as bijective, injective, or surjective based and report the actual size in bits of the transform.

C.4. Computational Efficiency. The computational efficiency of the k -mer transformations is a practical consideration, especially when dealing with large datasets. We measure the runtime and memory usage of each transformation to assess their computational overhead. Transformations with lower runtime and memory requirements are preferred for scalability and efficient processing.

Results

D. Datasets description. To encompass a broad spectrum of k -mer composition distributions, we selected four datasets, each possessing distinct characteristics:

1. **RAND:** A synthetic dataset comprising a random sequence of 100 megabases, serving as a benchmark to underscore the non-uniform distribution inherent in genomic sequences.
2. **CHRY:** The sequence of the human Y chromosome from the CHM13 assembly (23), chosen to exemplify complex and repetitive genomic content.
3. **GC75:** The complete genome of *Anaeromyxobacter dehalogenans*, spanning 5,029,329 nucleotides (GenBank id:CP001359.1, RefSeq Assembly GCF_000022145.1), characterized by an extreme GC content of 75.5%. This dataset represent genomes with high GC content.
4. **GC15:** The complete genome of *Candidatus Carsonella ruddii* (24) (GenBank id:CP003544.1, RefSeq Assembly GCF_000287295.1), consisting of 157,543 nucleotides with an extreme GC content of 14.5%. This dataset represent genomes with low GC content.

These datasets were chosen to highlight the diverse k -mer composition encountered in genomic sequences, ranging from synthetic randomness to extreme GC and repeated content variations.

Fig. 1. Distribution of suffixes for prefix lengths 8 for the RAND dataset.

E. k -mer prefix distribution. A first observation of Figure 1 is that all transforms (except Lyndon Minimizer and BWT) perform nearly perfectly on the random sequence. This is expected, as the random sequence should have uniformly distributed k -mers, and the discrepancies between random and genomic sequences highlight the interest of this work. The canonical transform display some small bin because of the loss of non canonical k -mers. We observe that both Minimizer and Lyndon display a highly uneven distribution with a large proportion of empty buckets and very large buckets. This is expected, as many Lyndon prefixes cannot occur (for example, only the TTT...TTT k -mer starts with T), and for similar reasons, only a subset of prefixes are actually minimizers. While similar argument holds for the BWT, we observe a much more even distribution. Although there is a substantial amount of empty buckets, there are no extremely large buckets as with Lyndon and Minimizer. On the CHRY data presented Figure 2 that include complex genomic patterns, we start to observe that naive k -mer representations such as Identity, Inverse, and Cyclic are quite uneven and display almost identical distributions. Hash-based transforms, InttHash and Gab, perform extremely well, both providing almost perfectly uniform distributions. Transforms based on permutations, PermutationNuc, PermutationBin, and ZigZag, perform better than naive transforms but do not reach the level of hashed transforms, with PermutationBin being the most uniform. Lyndon distribution is relatively unchanged in comparison to random, but Minimizer become even more skewed.

Fig. 2. Distribution of suffixes for prefix lengths 8 for the CHRY dataset.

Fig. 3. Distribution of suffixes for prefix lengths 8 for the GC75 dataset.

Fig. 4. Distribution of suffixes for prefix lengths 8 for the GC15 dataset.

On GC-biased genomes presented Figure 3 and 4, we observe that the hash-based methods still perform extremely well. PermutationBin also does not seem to be impacted by the biases and still performs relatively well. All the other functions suffer from the bias and perform worse on such biased sequences, but they maintain their relative behaviors.

A brief summary on those experiments could be

IntHash, Gab > PermutationBin > PermutationNucl, ZigZag > Identity, Cyclic, Reverse > Bwt > Minimizer > Lyndon

We benchmarked different prefix size in the Supplementary Materials Figure 9, 10, 11 and 12 and the relative performances of the different tools hardly changes.

F. Longest common prefix of successive k -mer. Based on previous observations, a natural deduction would be to conclude that hash-based methods are the best transform, providing almost perfect uniformity even in biased sequences. To provide a richer comparison, we also chose to evaluate the cache coherence permitted by such transforms, since in practice, k -mers are mostly inserted or queried from an input sequence, and putting k -mers into different substructures induces time-expensive cache misses. To evaluate such properties, our benchmark computes the longest common prefixes for successive k -mers in Figures 5, 6, 7 and 8.

A first general observation is that, contrary to the previous plot, the same global behavior is observed in the random and the different genomic sequences. IntHash, Gab, ZigZag, Identity, Inverse, and Cyclic all unsurprisingly display very low LCP values in all datasets. Also unsurprisingly, the Minimizer transform shows LCP values near, since the minimizer size for those plots is 8. BWT presents a large LCP over the dataset, but Lyndon displays an even larger one, justifying the interest in this transform for CBL. Both Lyndon and BWT show their interest at taking advantage on redundancies of real data, where they perform better than on the random data. Identity, Inverse, and Cyclic are also slightly improved, while hash-based methods are naturally not impacted.

Another summary of those experiment could be

Lyndon > BWT > Minimizer > Others

Discussion

Our benchmark effectively demonstrates the impact of using k -mer transforms, particularly in achieving uniform distribution and optimizing successive k -mer prefixes. While it is challenging to draw absolute conclusions on the best-performing transform due to the numerous strategies and parameters that could be tested, we highlight the performance of hashing transform and Lyndon transform in their respective categories. We also observe that the Burrows-Wheeler Transform (BWT) appears relatively efficient in both uniformity and shared prefix, justifying its potential use in tools that have not yet incorporated this k -mer transform. This observation suggests that the two metrics, uniformity and shared prefix, are not entirely orthogonal, as some cache coherence can be achieved with acceptable uniformity. This raises the question of how to further improve this

Fig. 5. Mean and standard deviation of LCP of successive k -mer for prefix lengths 8 for the RAND dataset.

Fig. 6. Mean and standard deviation of LCP of successive k -mer for prefix lengths 8 for the CHRY dataset.

Fig. 7. Mean and standard deviation of LCP of successive k -mer for prefix lengths 8 for the GC75 dataset.

Fig. 8. Mean and standard deviation of LCP of successive k -mer for prefix lengths 8 for the GC15 dataset.

compromise and explore possible trade-offs. Additionally, we note that transforms can benefit from genomic sequence bias compared to uniform sequences, which could motivate the development of parametric transforms tailored to the properties of the indexed sequence.

Our benchmark can be enhanced in several ways. First, we plan to offer distinct modes for handling reverse complements, including differentiating them from forward sequences and utilizing only canonical forms. We are also exploring various encoding strategies, such as the naive approach and one that minimizes entropy by collapsing a k -mer with its reverse complement, potentially saving one bit (25). We could also test the effect on k -mer encoding that could impact performances on biased sequences.

Furthermore, we intend to incorporate other transforms that benefit from locally sensitive hashing properties such as syncmers (26), and recent developments in minimizers (27) designed to improve robustness to substitutions. A larger range of parameters should also be considered, including studying the impact of k -mer size alongside transform parameters like minimizer size.

We also aim to test a wider set of input sequences, particularly to observe the transforms' behaviors in knowingly difficult scenarios, such as RNA-seq with highly skewed k -mer distributions, poly-As, homopolymers, and GC-rich regions. Another approach to evaluate complex scenarios would be to add a module that alters input sequences to modify their GC or homopolymer rate, allowing for the assessment of transform resistance to changing rates. Computing GC content compared to the input and analyzing dimer, trimer or tetramer compositions would also be interesting features to consider.

The display aspect could be improved by providing rankings or Pareto fronts to help users select the best-performing transforms. In order to compare more efficiently metrics to evaluate uniformity and cache locality should be introduced such as chi-squared test to compare the observed distribution of k -mers in the bins to the expected uniform distribution.

Pragmatically integrating well-performing transforms into existing tools like *RedOak* and *CBL* and investigating their performance is indeed one of the major goals of such a project.

Future work involves gaining a deeper understanding of the intrinsic costs associated with injective transformation. Specifically, we are interested in evaluating the additional costs of injective functions, such as those based on minimizers or k -mer rotations, which require extra information to recover the original sequence. More generally, we emphasize the interest in conceiving invertible functions that display cache-coherence properties in a cost-efficient manner.

Bibliography

- Anton Bankevich, Andrey V Bzikadze, Mikhail Kolmogorov, Dmitry Antipov, and Pavel A Pevzner. Multiplex de bruijn graphs enable genome assembly from long, high-fidelity reads. *Nature biotechnology*, 40(7):1075–1081, 2022.
- Antoine Limasset, Jean-François Flot, and Pierre Peterlongo. Toward perfect reads: self-correction of short reads via mapping on de bruijn graphs. *Bioinformatics*, 36(5):1374–1381, 2020.
- Nicolas L Bray, Harold Pimentel, Páll Melsted, and Lior Pachter. Near-optimal probabilistic rna-seq quantification. *Nature biotechnology*, 34(5):525–527, 2016.
- Sergei Mangul and David Koslicki. Reference-free comparison of microbial communities via de bruijn graphs. In *proceedings of the 7th ACM international conference on bioinformatics, computational biology, and health informatics*, pages 68–77, 2016.
- Thomas C Conway and Andrew J Bromage. Succinct data structures for assembling large genomes. *Bioinformatics*, 27(4):479–486, 2011.
- Brad Solomon and Carl Kingsford. Fast search of thousands of short-read sequencing experiments. *Nature biotechnology*, 34(3):300–302, 2016.
- Camille Marchet and Antoine Limasset. Scalable sequence database search using partitioned aggregated bloom comb trees. *Bioinformatics*, 39(Supplement_1):i252–i259, 2023.
- Amatur Rahman and Paul Medvedev. Representation of m -mer sets using spectrum-preserving string sets. In *International Conference on Research in Computational Molecular Biology*, pages 152–168. Springer, 2020.
- Ondřej Sladký, Pavel Veselý, and Karel Břinda. Masked superstrings as a unified framework for textual k -mer set representations. *bioRxiv*, pages 2023–02, 2023.
- Clément Agret, Annie Chateau, Gaetan Droc, Gautier Sarah, Manuel Ruiz, and Alban Mancheron. Redoak: a reference-free and alignment-free structure for indexing a collection of similar genomes. *Journal of Open Source Software*, 7(80):4363, 2022. doi: 10.21105/joss.04363.
- Savannah J Hoyt, Jessica M Storer, Gabrielle A Hartley, Patrick GS Grady, Ariel Gershman, Leonardo G de Lima, Charles Limouse, Reza Halabian, Luke Wojenski, Matias Rodriguez, et al. From telomere to telomere: The transcriptional and epigenetic state of human repeat elements. *Science*, 376(6588):eabk3112, 2022.
- Ratnesh Singh, Ray Ming, and Qingyi Yu. Comparative analysis of gc content variations in plant genomes. *Tropical Plant Biology*, 9:136–149, 2016.
- Allison Piovesan, Maria Chiara Pelleri, Francesca Antonaros, Pierluigi Strippoli, Maria Caracausi, and Lorenza Vitale. On the length, weight and gc content of the human genome. *BMC research notes*, 12:1–7, 2019.
- Prashant Pandey, Michael A Bender, Rob Johnson, and Rob Patro. A general-purpose counting filter: Making every bit count. In *Proceedings of the 2017 ACM international conference on Management of Data*, pages 775–787, 2017.
- Igor Martayan, Bastien Cazaux, Antoine Limasset, and Camille Marchet. Conway-bromage-lyndon (cbl): an exact, dynamic representation of k -mer sets. *bioRxiv*, pages 2024–01, 2024.
- Rayan Chikhi, Antoine Limasset, Shaun Jackman, Jared T Simpson, and Paul Medvedev. On the representation of de bruijn graphs. In *Research in Computational Molecular Biology: 18th Annual International Conference, RECOMB 2014, Pittsburgh, PA, USA, April 2-5, 2014, Proceedings 18*, pages 35–55. Springer, 2014.
- Giulio Ermanno Pibiri, Yoshihiro Shibuya, and Antoine Limasset. Locality-preserving minimal perfect hashing of k -mers. *Bioinformatics*, 39(Supplement_1):i534–i543, 2023.
- Camille Marchet, Mael Kerbiriou, and Antoine Limasset. Blight: efficient exact associative structure for k -mers. *Bioinformatics*, 37(18):2858–2865, 2021.
- Heng Li. Minimap2: pairwise alignment for nucleotide sequences. *Bioinformatics*, 34(18):3094–3100, 2018.
- Jens Zentgraf and Sven Rahmann. Fast gapped k -mer counting with subdivided multi-way bucketed cuckoo hash tables. In *22nd International Workshop on Algorithms in Bioinformatics (WABI 2022)*. Schloss Dagstuhl-Leibniz-Zentrum für Informatik, 2022.
- Joe Sawada and Aaron Williams. Practical algorithms to rank necklaces, lyndon words, and de bruijn sequences. *Journal of Discrete Algorithms*, 43:95–110, 2017.
- Heng Li and Richard Durbin. Fast and accurate short read alignment with burrows–wheeler transform. *Bioinformatics*, 25(14):1754–1760, 2009.
- Sergey Nurk, Sergey Koren, Arang Rhie, Mikko Rautiainen, Andrey V Bzikadze, Alla Mikheenko, Mitchell R Vollger, Nicolas Altomare, Lev Uralsky, Ariel Gershman, et al. The complete sequence of a human genome. *Science*, 376(6588):44–53, 2022.
- Daniel B Sloan and Nancy A Moran. Genome reduction and co-evolution between the primary and secondary bacterial symbionts of psyllids. *Molecular biology and evolution*, 29(12):3781–3792, 2012.
- Roland Wittler. General encoding of canonical k -mers. *Peer Community Journal*, 3, 2023.
- Robert Edgar. Syncmers are more sensitive than minimizers for selecting conserved k -mers in biological sequences. *PeerJ*, 9:e10805, 2021.
- Minh Hoang, Guillaume Marçais, and Carl Kingsford. Density and conservation optimization of the generalized masked-minimizer sketching scheme. *Journal of Computational Biology*, 31(1):2–20, 2024.

Supplementary Materials

Fig. 9. Distribution of suffixes for different prefix lengths for the RAND dataset.

Fig. 10. Distribution of suffixes for different prefix lengths for the CHRY dataset.

Fig. 11. Distribution of suffixes for different prefix lengths for the GC75 dataset.

Fig. 12. Distribution of suffixes for different prefix lengths for the GC15 dataset.